

«COMPUTERIZATION PROCESS OF TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE»

Odilova Gulchiroy Husniddin qizi

student of Andijan state institute of foreign languages, group 418

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7179170>

The current stage of computerization of education presupposes the use of a computer as a means of teaching, not one-time, but constantly, from the first to the last lesson in any type of education. The main problem in this case is contained in the technology of creating a computer course, which the student has to master. Either a complete reorganization and orientation towards the creation of new computerized courses, or the implementation of a methodology with partial computer support of the course, is acceptable. Computerization of education has a significant impact on all components of the modern educational system and, in particular, on the subject "Foreign language": its goals, objectives, content, methods, technology.

Teaching a foreign language using a computer has a number of advantages:

1. Students' interest in computers leads to high motivation of the learning process;
2. Pupils willingly conduct a dialogue with a computer, their general, computer and language culture is growing;
3. Individualization of training;
4. Ability to provide direct feedback;
5. The computer does not express negative emotions when repeating mistakes;
6. Objectivity of the assessment;
7. Effective performance of exercises and trainings is ensured.

A striking example of the use of computer technology in recent years became the possibility of learning on a distance basis. Distance learning is an autonomous form of education, and information technology in distance learning is the main tool. Today's distance learning is based on the use of the following essential elements: media of information transmission (mail, television, radio, information communication networks), methods that depend on the technical environment for the exchange of information. Distance learning is the interaction of a teacher and students with each other at a distance, reflecting all components characteristic of the educational process (goals, content, methods, organizational forms, teaching aids) and implemented by specific means of Internet technologies or other means that imply interactivity. Nevertheless, despite its extensive application, this system causes a lot of controversy, since all aspects have not been fully discovered.

The specificity of the discipline "Foreign language" is that the main component of the content of teaching a foreign language is not the foundations of the sciences, but methods of activity - teaching various types of speech activity: speaking, listening, reading, writing. You can learn speech activity only in live communication, and for this you need a partner. A computer program, a compact disc, no matter how interactive they are, can only provide communication with the machine. The only exception is telecommunications, when a student enters into a live dialogue (written or oral) with a real partner - a native speaker. It follows from this that in computer technologies the teacher is not the only carrier and owner of information, he is left with the author's approach to its interpretation. The focus of the goals is shifted towards the development of students' skills to work with information, the development of research skills. With traditional teaching, the communicative aspect of teaching a foreign language is carried out more effectively, which is why it is necessary to combine teaching a foreign language using a computer and traditional teaching.

Computer programs should be used as an important but complementary component of the curriculum, along with traditional materials and methods. When working with a computer, you inevitably have to change the entire structure of the lesson and, in general, its competence. It is necessary to specifically establish the appropriate role and place of the computer in the educational process, clarify and determine the basic concepts, introduce methodological and technical aspects. As practice shows, the computer has not yet become a full-fledged means of teaching at school. In particular, in order to achieve a positive effect from the use of information technologies, certain conditions must be met:

- temporary. Each subject of the school curriculum has its own organizational, methodological and substantive features, in accordance with which the moment of "inclusion" of information technologies in it should be chosen;
- technical. The technical characteristics of personal computers are different. Depending on the range of tasks that are supposed to be solved, it is necessary to select a computer and additional devices (such as a scanner, printer, modem, headphones, microphone, etc.). The scope of tasks determines the subject in the study of which the computer is used;
- organizational. When information technology is included in the process of studying a subject, the question of setting up software and setting up equipment arises. Not every teacher has the skills necessary for the complex maintenance of computer equipment or for the independent development of educational tools.

Therefore, it is obvious that the teacher needs a qualified assistant (for example, in the person of a laboratory assistant or a computer science teacher). If these conditions are met, according to experts, modern information technologies can serve as an effective didactic tool. The problems of using computer tools in the learning process are largely related to the readiness of a modern teacher to perceive a personal computer as a didactic tool.

References:

1. Baraldi, Enrico (2003), When Information Technology Faces Resource Interaction: Using IT Tools to Handle Products at IKEA and Edsbyn. Department of Business Studies, Uppsala University, Doctoral Thesis No. 105.
2. Polat ES, Bukharkina M. Yu., Moiseeva MV, Petrov AE New pedagogical and information technologies in the education system. - M., 2001.
3. Raitskaya L.K. Independent educational and cognitive activity in the information and educational environment of the Internet: a didactic concept under the scientific editorship of A.V. Gagarin. Moscow, 2012. / Site of scientific articles [Electronic resource] - Access mode:
http://elibrary.ru/query_results.asp.

